

Interview Guide

Let's start by talking about your experience in identifying problems on your own:

1. Have you been able to find more problems since our last meeting? If so, are they problems you already knew about or ones you noticed through the catalog?
2. How was your interaction with the catalog during the past week? Did you consult it again? If so, at what moment?
3. Did you use the catalog while developing any activity? If yes, how was that experience?

Now, talking about the problem identification process as a whole:

4. Was the catalog useful in identifying problems in the architecture you work with? If yes, how? If not, why?
5. Was the catalog useful in proposing solutions for the identified problems? If yes, how? If not, why?
6. If you were to recommend the catalog to a colleague, how would you suggest they use it? And you, do you intend to use the catalog again? In what way?
7. Are there problems you had not noticed or did not know about until you found them in the catalog? If yes, which ones?
8. Do you have suggestions for new anti-patterns or new solutions for the existing anti-patterns? If yes, which ones?
9. Did you identify any challenges and/or benefits when using the catalog during problem identification? Did you have any difficulty understanding any anti-pattern, whether the problem or the solution?
10. Finally: Do you have any suggestions for improving the catalog? How could it be improved to better support Micro Frontends development?